

HUMAN RIGHTS AND CIVIL SOCIETY UNDER GLOBALIZATION

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Abstract. *This article studies and analyzes the issues of human rights and civil society in today's globalization. In particular, he looks at the practical processes of paying attention to human rights and taking into account the needs of citizens in our country.*

Keywords: *human rights, civil society, conditions of globalization, human problems, human and state relations, globalization phenomenon.*

It is known that the main concept describing the processes of world development in the early years of the 21st century was globalization. Its essence lays in the sharp expansion, including the complexity, of the relations and interdependence of people and states, manifested in the processes of forming the planetary information space, the world market of capital, goods and labor, and the internationalization of human problems. Based on this, it can be said that the topic of the phenomenon of globalization goes beyond the purely economic sphere, which many researchers tend to interpret, and covers almost all spheres of social activity, as well as politics, ideology, culture, lifestyle and conditions of human existence.

The information revolution, which provides the technical basis for the creation of global information networks, the internationalization of capital and the strengthening of competition in world markets, the scarcity of natural resources and the strengthening of the struggle for control, are the necessary conditions of the processes of globalization. In Burundi, in the world, they increase the risk of demographic explosion, as well as the increase of man-made load on nature and the spread of weapons of mass destruction. These facts, despite their differences, are closely related to each other, and their interaction determines the complexity and contradictions of globalization processes. Information technologies create a real opportunity to dramatically accelerate the economic, scientific, cultural development and integration of our planet, to unite humanity into a single society that understands its interests and responsibility for the fate of the world. They can also become a tool to divide the world and fuel conflict. In this context, the role of human rights, civil society and its institutions is currently being updated.

In order to answer the question of the fate of the state in the current era of globalization, it shows the need for a detailed review of human rights, in particular, the institutions of civil society, the spheres covered by the globalization process - economic and financial, socio-political and ecological, cultural and other spheres.

Globalization changes the roles and functions of traditional social institutions, including the institutional credo of civil society. Civil society organizations must deal with intractable issues that lie beyond national territorial jurisdictions.

During the years of independence, a solid foundation of our national statehood was established in Uzbekistan, the rule of law and human rights, life, freedom, honor and dignity and other inalienable rights enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan were ensured.

The development of Uzbekistan in the new millennium is determined by the transformation of the country, its entry into the world community as an independent entity. This is an important

component of the globalizing world in the post-industrial era. The modern global order is increasingly defined by multifaceted and interdependent patterns of transnational relations formed by state and non-state actors. Its specific features are openness, complexity, interdependence, and inconsistency, which do not correspond to the level of development of human rights, civil institutions, and civil culture in Uzbekistan, which raises questions about the fate of the country in the context of globalization.

In modern scientific literature, the problems of human rights, civil society and globalization are often revealed in political, legal and economic aspects. International terrorism, increase in crime, devaluation of human life, decline of morals and culture make the socio-philosophical and ideological aspects of the problem more urgent.

In Uzbekistan, issues of promotion, protection and observance of human rights are one of the priorities of the state policy. In 2017-2021, specific goal-oriented measures were implemented in the field of ensuring personal, political, economic, social and cultural rights within the framework of the Action Strategy for the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026, which is a logical continuation of the action strategy, was adopted. In this document, the trends of Uzbekistan's development in the near and medium term, directions for comprehensive development of all aspects of state and community life have been clearly defined.

The importance of the development strategy lies in the fact that the existing problems are taken into account in its development, and the current tasks awaiting solution are reflected. Most importantly, our people actively participated in the development of this program document. As the head of our state noted, we set the principle of "For human dignity" as the main criterion of all our reforms. In order to implement the noble idea of "the state is for the people", we developed the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 in direct consultation with our people, based on the opinions and suggestions of our people. In all this lies the development of human rights and civil society.

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Civil society and the rule of law are interrelated. For this reason, every decision and decree, laws, and issues related to human rights and civil society are reflected.

Today, issues of civil society and human rights are not left out of the eyes of international civil institutions. The growing role of international civil institutions also changes the meaning and functions of state power: it is transformed from a mechanism of suffocation of society into a force for democratic and intellectual decision-making of common affairs, turning it not only into a legal institution, but also society, as well as its balanced development support, it will become a social, spiritual, intellectual center designed to protect the interests of individual citizens and individual regions and local communities that are part of the constituent entities of the country.

The globalization of relations in the world community makes the problem of the globalization of civil society, human rights, that is, the sphere of ideas, values, institutions, organizations, networks, citizens located between the family, the state and the market, operating outside of national societies; policies and economies that focus on people's interests and needs; personal security concepts; new models of sustainable development, their goal is to invest in

human potential and create an environment that allows full use of human abilities; cooperation between government and markets; new models of national and global management, their goal is to meet the growth of human needs against the background of the gradual decline of the state; acknowledges the relevance of international cooperation forms that should be directed not to the preference of the state's interests, but to the needs of the population, namely, people, citizens.

The specific features of social life in the country in the current period are determined by the complex transition stage in the formation of the statehood of Uzbekistan. In this case, the task of the state is to find optimal opportunities to become a global civil society in order to correctly represent national structures in solving modern conflicts.

Summing up from the above, it should be said that the theoretical and methodological basis of the problem is the scientific principles of specific historical, systematic, socio-philosophical, dialectical and synergetic approaches developed in classical works, as well as philosophy, political science, sociology and scientific methodology, modern literature. Speaking about its practical and theoretical importance, the results and information obtained as a result of studies are of important conceptual and methodological importance, and they form an adequate point of view about the genesis and state of civil society, the issue of human rights, it allows clarifying its specific features on a global scale, influencing the formation of civil culture.

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